

ANDROID-BASED LEARNING MATERIALS IN GENETICS

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Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics

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Abstract

The study focused mainly with the development of Android-based Learning Materials in Genetics based from the Curriculum Guide of Senior High School given by the Department of Education conducted at Morong National High School – Senior High School School Year 2021-2022. The topics are included in the Curriculum Guide of General Biology 2 based on the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum for Senior High School – Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) Track. The study included the evaluation of the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics through a modified evaluation tool for quantitative analysis of data. The study employed the Developmental and Descriptive methods of Research specifically, in describing the development of the mobile application and assessing the quality of the developed learning material through the utilization of a Questionnaire-Checklists for the two groups of respondents which are the twenty (20) Teachers of Science and twenty (20) Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Experts as they were capable to objectively evaluate the developed learning material in terms of instructional content, alignment to the curriculum, depth of knowledge, learner engagement interactivity, graphics and multimedia, lay-outs, operation, and performance. Based on the intensified treatment of the data gathered, the Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics was designed and constructed aligned to the learning competencies of the current curriculum. The evaluation of the developed mobile application in terms of instructional content, alignment to the curriculum, depth of knowledge, learner engagement interactivity, graphics and multimedia, lay-outs, operation, and performance had a 100% Highly Agree as interpretation on the developed material. In the light of the summary of the findings, it is concluded that the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics was generally efficient, simple to learn, easy to navigate, appealing and engaging. It was also pedagogically constructive as the content and the tools used in the application were useful from the perspective of both the content experts and the ICT experts. Thus, accomplishing the primary goal of this research study by providing effective instruction through mobile learning. Based from the results of evaluation and conclusion on the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics, the following are hereby recommended: the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics can be used to facilitate teaching-learning process. The developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics maybe subjected to revision and modifications in the future depending on the needed competency for a particular topic and the needs and abilities and sustainability of learning styles of the future learners. It may be subjected for improvement to be utilized in iOS or apple devices. The developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics may be modified for an automatic update of the content. Encourage other teachers in science specifically Biology teachers to use the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics. Additional studies maybe conducted with regards to more content-based courses to be placed in other areas that could supplement the findings of this study.

Keywords: *android, learning, genetics*

Introduction

Education is indeed a continuous process. As the idea suggests that there is no permanent thing in this world but change, education is also changing as the technology is advancing from time to time. Each generation found out that the education nowadays they have in is technology-advanced than seemed years ago. As years go by, many things were discovered and more ideas were explored which yields to the discovery of more effective products.

As modern technology advances from time to time, education also advances. One of the newest methods that teachers are actually using in their teaching process is the use of Technology coupled with internet.

Aquino (2019) cited that Technological advancement has been unavoidable in all walks of life. Education is not an exemption. As we are gearing toward advanced teaching and learning process, we seek to cope up with the needs and demands of 21st Century Learning brought about by the so called “21st Century Learners” and so teachers have to adapt to themselves to become “21st Century Teachers”.

Andaya (2017) stated that the first step to enhancing the quality of Education is by closing the technological gaps in information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the Philippines, as cited by the Department of Education’s Bureau of Curriculum Development. As stipulated in Department of Education Memorandum No. 20, series of 2013, teachers should maximize the utilization of various packages of Instructional Materials to ensure “creative, interactive, interesting, meaningful and enjoyable learning activities in the day-to-day life of the students” (Education Summit, 2017).

The use of technology inside the classrooms in order to make the education relevant is stipulated in Article XIV, Section 10 of 1987 Philippine Constitution which states:

“Science and Technology are essential for national development and progress. The state shall give priority to research and development, invention and utilization and to science and technology, education, training and services. It shall support indigenous, appropriate and self-reliant scientific and technological capabilities and their application to the country’s productive system on national life.”

It is clearly stated in the law that there is really a need to develop instructional materials or evaluate instructional materials, like the developed and prepared technology-based resources. In this manner, this can enhance the teaching – learning process which will result to better performance of students.

According to Montemayor (2018), educators are urged to foster creativity in coming up with various materials that are Information and Communication Technology (ICT) based; these materials that are ICT-based includes the use of various modern software devices, and the most accessible nowadays is the use of Android application.

Android is based on the Linux kernel, and developed by Google and later the Open Handset Alliance. It is also software platform and OS for mobile devices and permits developers to write code within the Java language, dominant the device via Google developed Java libraries. It will run on many various devices from many different manufactures. Android includes a software package development kit (SDK) that helps people write original code and assemble software package modules to form apps for android users. Android also provides a platform to distribute apps. All at once, android represents an ecosystem for mobile apps. Android could be a freely downloadable open source software package stack for mobile devices that has an OS, middleware and key applications supported LINUX and Java. (Asritha, 2020)

Nowadays, android is an emerging technology that is used in Smart Phones which has changed the lives of everyone. It provides an easy access to information and communication as one may use certain application that are utilized in various activities such as social networking, messaging, entertainment and even in education.

Li Ma (2014) cited that as the Android operating system is getting more popular, the application based on Android SDK attracts much more attention. The interfaces of the Android apps are pretty and the operation is smooth so that users are able to manipulate apps more conveniently and smoothly.

In today’s world, smartphones have become essential as most people rely on them for daily communication. Numerous applications are created to enhance entertainment and functionality, and the Android operating system has emerged as a leading choice in the smartphone market (Verma, 2018).

As android phones and its applications are becoming so familiar in many people around the world, android is considered as a good platform for teachers to facilitate learning in their classes as it aids in providing a more comprehensive and accessible instructional materials that teachers and learners use in day-to-day instructions and learning specially, in the time of pandemic where face-to-face classes and the use of papers and tangible materials are restricted, and the country is experiencing inadequacy of e-learning materials to be provided for distance learning.

As the survey conducted by the researchers revealed, inadequate e-learning resources is another difficulty that repetitively appears in the responses of the students. Most students use only phone and need other resources (“I would need laptop and printer to study and really accomplish my requirements well” -Student 19). Others have a challenge in terms of the storage capacity of their available gadgets (“Not enough space in phone memory due to applications like Zoom, Moodle, Google Meet, and Adobe Reader -Student 7). (McCombes, 2022)

Meanwhile, the findings of the studies (e.g. Coleman, 2011; and Henaku, 2020) corroborate the other result of this study in which inadequate learning resources are among the difficulties confronting the students. This result may imply that students cannot completely participate in and benefit from remote learning. This also confirms the findings of Saavedra (2020) that access to remote learning devices like computers has been a recurring challenge for students as schools shift to online distance learning in the middle of a global health emergency.

This problem may stem from financial-related problems as another difficulty disclosed by student participants. This finding is the same as that of Matswetu et al., (2013) in which students in Zimbabwe faced financial problems in a distance learning set-up. The current crisis has made it even more difficult for the students surveyed who articulated difficulty in finding a job to support their learning needs. Noteworthy, in the Philippines, financial struggles have started to worsen for poor families during the outbreak due to an unprecedented economic shutdown (Adele, 2020).

With android-based instructional media which collaborate with cooperative learning model, the problem about the lack of learning materials may be solved as it provides paperless self-learning modules, interactive activities, and assessments to ensure the continuity of quality learning in times of pandemic.

It is expected to create a learning environment that is effective and efficient that will make students become interested in learning because the media is able to show an interesting animation. It is then able to develop the mindset of students become more creative.

Even in times of Pandemic, teachers want their students to understand the details of the lesson for more than a week rather than memorizing facts. Teachers are finding it challenging to teach an ever-increasing amount of material. The effect of technology such as

the utilization of android devices and applications on motivation and retention in covering a broad curriculum, results in students' solid memories (Granito et al., 2012).

Teachers as facilitators of learning should have a very significant role to this consideration must be literate enough to utilize modern methods of learning; thus, one must consider the use of android application in transferring content to the students.

The Education Act of 1982 known as *Batas Pambansa Blg. 232* stated that

“The teacher must sustain interest and enthusiasm in improving instruction so that he may be able to maximize learning capabilities of his students. He must also be aware of the role of formal education where the government has made its policy to gear higher education towards the provision of quality education”

In this modern –day educational system, the use of android apps does not only triggers interest of the students but also engage them to the reality of learning which acquire a better understanding of the subjects being discussed by the teacher in lined with the Curriculum.

In this study, Android operating system was preferred since it enables free software and it is frequently used. According to IDC (2015), Android and IOS mobile operating systems account for 96.3% of all smartphone shipments. IDC data also clearly shows that the Android mobile operating system is the most common operating system in the world (Android 32%, IOS 27%). Android has an 86.8% share of the smartphone market and IOS has a market share of 12.5% with 45.5 million shipments (IDC, 2016b). One of the most important reasons of this is that Android devices have a wide range of prices that everyone can buy (IDC, 2015).

The researcher, therefore in this study, agree with the significance of the use of Android Application in the teaching-learning process like the developed multi-media materials in different academic subjects in both elementary and high school. The common multi-media materials in which teachers are using are the power point presentation, acetate materials, animations, pictures, movie makers and video clips which will be more accessible for students if they will be using android applications instead of these in common learning materials, specially in this times of pandemic where self-learning and distance learning is encouraged.

Research Questions

This study aimed to:

1. To describe the development of Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics.
2. To evaluate the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics by the experts:
 - 2.1. Science teachers:
 - 2.1.1. instructional Content;
 - 2.1.2. alignment to the Curriculum;
 - 2.1.3. depth of Knowledge;
 - 2.1.4. learner Engagement Interactivity;
 - 2.2. ICT experts:
 - 2.2.1. graphics and multimedia;
 - 2.2.2. lay-outs;
 - 2.2.3. operation;
 - 2.2.4. performance?
3. To offer recommendations for the improvement of the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used the Descriptive and Developmental methods of research. The descriptive and developmental study is used to attain the desired evaluation of the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics.

Developmental studies deal with the physical planet, curriculum and teaching methods and their efforts on the characteristics of learners are examples given by Sevilla et al. Thus, this method may result to the development of instructional material designed for the teachers and learners.

Ibrahim (2016) describes the Developmental research as one of the most fundamental research methodology employed when developing instructional materials to facilitate instruction. For this essence, developmental research becomes an area of discussion like a mantra in literature of the instructional technology.

This design serves as a guide for the researcher and a big help in gathering data through adopted questionnaire checklist that cleared status of the phenomenon at the time of research on the evaluation of the Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics.

The descriptive research design involves observing and collecting data on a given topic without attempting to infer cause-and-effect relationships. The goal of descriptive research is to provide a comprehensive and accurate picture of the population or phenomenon being studied and to describe the relationships, patterns, and trends that exist within the data.

Descriptive research design can include surveys, observational studies, and case studies, and the data collected can be qualitative or quantitative. The findings from descriptive research provide valuable insights and inform future research, but do not establish cause-and-effect relationships.

McCombes (2022), cited that Descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation or phenomenon. It can answer what, where, when and how questions, but not why questions. So descriptive researchers investigate meanings, interpretations, symbols, and the processes.

The principal aim in employing this method is to describe the nature of the situation as it existed at the time of study, explored the causes of particular phenomena.

This study used the descriptive method of research through the use of researcher and developer's direct observations in the process of development of the learning material. The gathered data through the observation was used in describing the development of the learning material.

Respondents

The subject of the study is the development of Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics. The Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics is a Mobile Learning Application that provides Teachers of Science and students to have a productive learning experience. It provides collected, selected and organized lessons, videos, activities and assessments to enhance the acquisition of knowledge and skills in which learners can access anytime because of its offline feature.

The developed Mobile Application is designed to provide students with information, background, ideas and insights to help them understand the process better. Each lesson in the mobile application includes various activities to enhance further the learning of the students. Videos are also available offline to support the lessons. Assessment through digital quiz is also available to test the learning of the students in which scores are automatically generated after each set of assessment.

Furthermore, twenty (20) Science Teachers who are teaching the discipline for 5 years and above from various schools in the Division of Rizal and twenty (20) ICT experts served as respondents/experts in evaluating the Acceptability of the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in terms of instructional content, alignment to the curriculum, depth of knowledge, learner engagement interactivity, graphics and multimedia, lay-outs, operation and performance.

Instrument

The study was done through collecting data by means of the adapted and modified questionnaire-checklist which served as the instrument of the study.

The study was based on the least mastered skills in the Curriculum Guide (CG) in General Biology 2, School Year 2021-2022 prescribed by the Department of Education to develop the Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics. The developed Android-Based learning materials are composed of lessons, digital activities, videos, and digital assessment orb quiz that will help in improving the learners' understanding and critical thinking in Genetics.

To identify the proficiency of the users in utilizing an android device, the researcher conducted a Survey to the teachers and learners of Morong National Senior High School. The result of the survey showed that the teachers and learners are advanced when it comes to the use of android devices and application. Thus, developing a digital learning material like the Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics was a good platform to enhance the learners' competency in Genetics.

The researcher used the adapted questionnaire-checklist from the study of Picones (2015) entitled "Trigonometry Interactive Mobile App".

To further evaluate the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics, the researcher administered the adapted and modified Questionnaire-Checklist to the respondents. The respondents are twenty (20) teachers of science from the district of Morong, and twenty (20) ICT experts.

The twenty (20) Teachers of Science who were chosen as respondents are teachers from the Division of Rizal, district of Morong, teaching General Biology 2 for at least five (5) years and above; and the twenty (20) ICT Experts who are Information, Communication and Technology Staffs from Rizal Province who have experiences in developing mobile applications for 5 years were also chosen as respondents. Overall, there were 40 respondents. The age range of the respondents is from 28 to 56 years old.

The adapted and modified questionnaire checklist prepared by the researcher has been anchored from the principles of instructional design by Dr. Robert Gagne as it has been administered to the respondents.

Procedure

The study was conducted at the Division of Rizal, District of Morong for the School Year 2021-2022.

The researcher proposed three (3) titles and defended each title to the panellists. After a thorough discussion and explanation, the

panellists came up with the proposed title “Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics”, then the needed information and related literature and studies were gathered to support the study.

After the title defense, the researcher started to gather related studies for the development of the paper proposal.

After the colloquium and evaluation of the thesis proposal, the researcher planned, designed and developed the proposed product of the study which is the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics.

The researcher adapted and modified a Questionnaire-Checklist with Eight (8) aspects or parameters: Instructional content, alignment to the curriculum, depth of knowledge and learner engagement interactivity were the aspects assessed by the teachers of science; and graphics and multimedia, lay-outs, operation and performance were the aspects assessed by the ICT experts.

The researcher administered the developed Questionnaire-checklist to the respondents: twenty (20) teachers of science from the district of Morong and twenty (20) ICT Experts from Rizal Province.

The researcher provided a digital copy of the developed learning material, installed to their android phones, used it and evaluated using the developed Questionnaire-Checklist.

After the evaluation of the respondents, the researcher gathered the data, and undergone correct statistical analysis in the University Statistical Center. The researcher included the result of the statistical analysis and constructed the final manuscript of the study.

As the final defense was already done, the researcher revised the manuscript through incorporating the suggestions of the thesis adviser and panel members and developed the final manuscript of the study and submitted it to the University Graduate Library.

Data Analysis

To determine the evaluation of the two (2) groups of respondents on the quality of the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics with respect to different criteria: instructional content, alignment to the curriculum, depth of knowledge, learner engagement interactivity, graphics and multimedia, lay-outs, operation and performance, mean was used.

To discuss the comments and suggestions of the Science Teachers and ICT Experts on the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics, qualitative discussion was used.

Results and Discussion

Evaluation of the Experts on the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials In Genetics

Table 1 presents the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Instructional Content.

Table 1. *Computed Mean on the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Instructional Content*

<i>Instructional Content</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Information is accurate, complete, and current	4.85	Highly Agree
Facts come from reliable sources which are clearly identified	4.70	Highly Agree
Content and context are consistent with the theme	4.70	Highly Agree
All information relates to the stated purpose and learning goals	4.75	Highly Agree
Overall	4.75	Highly Agree

The table above shows the result of the evaluation of science teacher on the developed learning material in terms of instructional content where the accuracy, completeness and up-to datedness was rated with a mean of 4.85, verbally interpreted as highly agree. With all the benchmark statements verbally interpreted as highly agree, the overall mean obtained was 4.75 which is equally verbally interpreted as highly agree.

These mean that the developed instructional material conforms with the enumerated parameters in terms of content making it a highly agreeable based on the evaluation of the science teachers.

The findings imply that the content of the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics possesses all the characteristics that makes up the complete, accurate and current instructional contents of the lessons, activities and assessment which are based on facts and reliable sources. Furthermore, the developed learning material is appropriate as indicated on the result of the evaluation of the Teachers of Science.

This confirms the findings of Sofos and Darra (2014) that appropriate planning of the content of the lesson, as well as its proper implementation, by enhancing the active role of teachers and students, contributes to the improvement of the educational process; which explains that the instructional content should be carefully planned, with accuracy, consistency and with reliable sources.

Chong and Kong (2012) cited that study of the content develops cooperation and communication among teachers and learners and strengthens friendly interpersonal relationships. This imply that properly planning of the instructional lesson content provides clear

delivery of instruction to the learners and therefore creating an atmosphere of cooperation in the teaching-learning process.

Table 2 presents the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Alignment to the Curriculum.

Table 2. *Computed Mean on the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Alignment to the Curriculum*

<i>Alignment to the Curriculum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Content are based from the current Curriculum Guide	4.90	Highly Agree
Learning competencies are evident in the Lessons	4.65	Highly Agree
Lists all prerequisite skills	4.55	Highly Agree
Assessment is relevant to the learning goals	4.80	Highly Agree
Overall	4.73	Highly Agree

It is depicted from the table that the result of the evaluation of the teachers of science on the developed learning material in terms of Alignment to the Curriculum was rated with an overall mean of 4.73 which is verbally interpreted as highly agree.

The results declare that the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics can be used for instruction and could contribute much in the teaching-learning process as the content are aligned to the current curriculum and relevant to the learning goals.

This confirmed the findings of Karakus (2021) that curriculum process affect educational environment and implementation. This means that in developing an instructional material, the developer or creator must consider its alignment to the curriculum.

Ark (2017) also said that curriculum typically refers to the knowledge and skills students are expected to learn, which includes the learning standards or learning objectives they are expected to meet; the units and lessons that teachers teach; the assignments and projects given to students; the books, materials, videos, presentations, and readings used in a course; and the tests, assessments, and other methods used to evaluate student learning. An individual teacher's curriculum, for example, would be the specific learning standards, lessons, assignments, and materials used to organize and teach a particular course.

All these literatures prove that alignment to the Curriculum must be considered in developing an instructional material.

Table 3 presents the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Depth of Knowledge.

Table 3. *Computed Mean on the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Depth of Knowledge*

<i>Depth of Knowledge</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Content promotes mastery and in-depth learning among learners	4.60	Highly Agree
Content knowledge is integrated with other learning area	4.50	Highly Agree
Content knowledge facilitates innovative learners within and across the curriculum	4.80	Highly Agree
Uses all real-world examples to make the instructions relevant to the learner	4.75	Highly Agree
Overall	4.66	Highly Agree

It can be gleaned from the table that the result of the evaluation of the teachers of science on the developed learning material in terms of Depth of Knowledge was rated with an overall mean of 4.66 which is verbally interpreted as highly agree.

This implies that the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics consists of lessons, learning activities and assessment that convey deeper knowledge and information that can be used by the teachers as it promotes mastery and in-depth learning among students.

The results were supported by Walkup (2014) says in his blog, "With Depth of Knowledge, context is everything". When planning for teaching and learning with depth of knowledge, consider how deeply or extensively you want your students to go with their learning. Establish the scenario, setting, or situation teaching and learning will be developed, delivered, and demonstrated.

At the same time, this result is supported by the findings of Polkas & Touloumis, (2012) which shows that the main advantages attributed to the use of the teaching planning are firstly the ability to provide the teacher with a reflection on the context of a metacognitive process that directs his/her pedagogical and didactic choices and feedbacks the educational process by putting an end to it in mechanically repetitive operations, and secondly, the possibility for the teacher to have effective plans, as good practices, to be revised, shared and reused in future teaching situations. This explains the importance of the depth of knowledge of the content in the instructional materials which allows learners to facilitate critical thinking and metacognition.

All these related literatures support the finding that depth of knowledge is indeed an important aspect in creating an instructional material like the present study.

Table 4 presents the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms

of Learner Engagement Interactivity.

Table 4. *Computed Mean on the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Learner Engagement Interactivity*

<i>Learner Engagement Interactivity</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Always requires learners to become actively engaged in order to learn	4.90	Highly Agree
Text and documents always employ multimedia enhancements to make learning interactive	4.75	Highly Agree
Provides appropriate feedback throughout instruction	4.80	Highly Agree
Keenly motivates the learners to continue learning and master concepts	4.90	Highly Agree
Overall	4.84	Highly Agree

It can be seen from the table that the result of the evaluation of the teachers of science on the developed learning material in terms of Learner Engagement Interactivity was rated with an overall mean of 4.84 which is verbally interpreted as highly agree.

This connotes that the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics possesses all the qualities of a good instructional material in which learners are easily engaged to the learning process, and interact through the use of multimedia enhancing the skills to be developed, the style sustains learning interest and stimulates the learners' thinking skills, habits and attitudes.

The result is supported by the idea of Wiana, Barliana, and Riyanto (2018) that the use of interactive multimedia in learning will increase efficiency, motivation and student-centered learning; this shows that the developed learning material is interactive and engaging among the users.

Taurina (2015) cited that student motivation is a significant factor in achieving learning outcomes. Therefore, there is a need to increase students' learning motivation, so that the learning outcomes are also more maximized. This explains that motivation increases as learners are engaged in the teaching-learning process.

Table 5 presents the composite table on the evaluation of the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics by the Teachers of Science in terms of Instructional Content, Alignment to the Curriculum, Depth of Knowledge, and Learner Engagement Interactivity.

Table 5. *Composite Table on the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in terms of Instructional Content, Alignment to the Curriculum, Depth of Knowledge, and Learner Engagement Interactivity*

<i>Aspects</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Instructional Content	4.75	Highly Agree
Alignment to the Curriculum	4.73	Highly Agree
Depth of Knowledge	4.66	Highly Agree
Learner Engagement Interactivity	4.84	Highly Agree
Grand Mean	4.74	Highly Agree

It can be gleaned from Table 1 that the parameters as evaluated by the Teachers of Science, the Learner Engagement Interactivity obtained the mean of 4.84 and interpreted as Highly Agree, the Instructional Content which obtained the mean of 4.75 and interpreted as Highly Agree. The Alignment to the Curriculum obtained the mean of 4.73 and interpreted as Highly Agree, and the Depth of Knowledge which obtained the mean of 4.66 and interpreted as Highly Agree. The Grand Mean is 4.74, all with an interpretation of Highly Agree. The results connote that the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics was very highly accepted by the teachers of Science in terms of Instructional Content, Alignment to the Curriculum, Depth of Knowledge, and Learner Engagement Interactivity.

This confirmed the findings of Marces (2020) that good instructional materials improves the performances of the students. Likewise, Ogaba (2013) said that it is important that the teachers in develop and prepare proper and efficient instructional materials for the delivery of instruction.

Table 6 presents the Evaluation of the ICT Experts on the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Graphics and Multimedia.

Table 6. *Computed Mean on the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Graphics and Multimedia*

<i>Graphics and Multimedia</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Graphics are well-designed and rendered to enhance learning.	4.80	Highly Agree
Background and text are pleasing, compatible and easy to read.	4.70	Highly Agree
Graphics are consistent, appropriate and designed to optimize learning.	4.75	Highly Agree
Colors are used in an effective way.	4.60	Highly Agree
Overall	4.71	Highly Agree

The table shows that the result of the evaluation of the ICT experts on the developed learning material in terms of Graphics and Multimedia was rated with an overall mean of 4.71 which is verbally interpreted as highly agree.

The results convey the impression that the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics consists of Graphics, animations, and multimedia aspects that are well-designed and rendered to enhance the teaching-learning process.

This supports the contention of Ghavifekr and Rosdy (2016), that teacher's preparation that is assisted with ICT is one of the main factors in the success of technology-based teaching and learning. The use of ICT in developing instructional materials allows a more defined graphics and multimedia which provides learners quality audio-visual presentations.

Rajendra and Sudana (2018) also cited that Interactive multimedia technology in the learning process can improve interactions between teachers and students. The quality of the instructional materials when it comes to design, graphics and animations leads to a more engaging and interactive discussions.

Table 7 presents the Evaluation of the ICT Experts on the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Lay-Outs.

Table 7. *Computed Mean on the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Terms of Lay-outs*

<i>Lay-outs</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Lay-out is clear and intuitive; learners can always find what they need	4.85	Highly Agree
It is easy to navigate through the information to find necessary feature.	4.40	Highly Agree
Layout is logical.	4.80	Highly Agree
Layout is consistent on all pages.	4.80	Highly Agree
Overall	4.71	Highly Agree

The table shows that the result of the evaluation of the ICT experts on the developed learning material in terms of Lay-outs was rated with an overall mean of 4.71 which is verbally interpreted as highly agree.

The results imply that the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics consists of lay-outs that is consistent on all pages, clear, intuitive and easy to navigate through the information so the learners can accessibly find their need.

This is supported by the idea of Janowski (2013) that lay-outs enable to use similar user interface elements across the application, what obviously increases the speed of writing the project. Layout design is also useful for determining the general look and feel of the application, which is important for increasing the ease of use of the final application.

According to Annamalai (2016), to get students' attention in multimedia, it should be designed with visuals, animation and video. This confirmed the result of findings that the developed mobile application has a well-designed lay-outs as a learning materials.

Table 8 presents the Evaluation of the ICT Experts on the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Operation.

Table 8. *Computed Mean on the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Operation*

<i>Operation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
The mobile application runs offline.	5.00	Highly Agree
The mobile application supports multi-tasking.	4.45	Highly Agree
Operates in different android operating systems (older and new versions of OS)	4.25	Highly Agree
It consists of organized flow of pages or screen casts.	4.80	Highly Agree
Overall	4.63	Highly Agree

The table shows that the result of the evaluation of the ICT experts on the developed learning material in terms of Operation was rated with an overall mean of 4.63 which is verbally interpreted as highly agree.

The results declare that the developed mobile application can operate properly offline, supports multi-tasking, runs in different android operating systems, and consists of organized flow of pages which make the learning material accessible for the learners who has old types of gadgets and have no internet connection.

This is supported by Jayatilleke (2016) which emphasized that operating the mobile learning application is more effective when it operates even offline.

Mobile learning offers benefits such as quick access to information for students, diverse ways of learning, contextual learning, control over own learning, supporting and encouraging learning, increased participation in the course, will to use in the course and positive meaningful differences of academic achievement, in terms with the operation of the mobile application.

Svihla (2014) stated that operations on mobile learning application like interactive learning assessments is useful with the students. This confirms the result that the developed mobile application can operate with multi-tasking and has assessments that are interactive.

Table 9 presents the Evaluation of the ICT Experts on the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Performance.

Table 9. *Computed Mean on the Evaluation of the Teachers of Science on the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in Terms of Performance*

<i>Performance</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>VI</i>
Fast loading screen casts are evident.	4.95	Highly Agree
Absence of bugs in the software.	4.55	Highly Agree
All parts are easy to access	4.95	Highly Agree
Scores in assessment are automatically computed.	4.90	Highly Agree
Overall	4.84	Highly Agree

The table shows that the result of the evaluation of the ICT experts on the developed learning material in terms of Performance was rated with an overall mean of 4.84 which is verbally interpreted as highly agree.

This imply that the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics performs smoothly – with fast loading screen as it has no bugs in the software itself, all parts are easy to access and computations in assessment part are automatically generated.

Miangah and Nezarat (2012) mentioned that a mobile application with high abilities or performance stretch out into human life, remote specialized gadgets have become open for almost everybody all over the place. This explains that mobile learning applications which perform with fast loading screen casts and has no bugs are definitely considered one of the best learning material in the world today.

This findings confirmed Jayatilleke (2016) in his study that the development of mobile application for learning with appropriate and good performance promotes effective learning.

Table 10 presents the composite table on the evaluation of the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics by the ICT Experts in terms of Graphics and Multimedia, Lay-outs, Operation and Performance.

Table 10. *Composite Table on the Evaluation of the ICT Experts on the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics in terms of Graphics and Multimedia, Lay-outs, Operation and Performance*

<i>Aspects</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
Graphics and Multimedia	4.71	Highly Agree
Lay-outs	4.71	Highly Agree
Operation	4.63	Highly Agree
Performance	4.84	Highly Agree
Grand Mean	4.72	Highly Agree

It can be gleaned from Table 10 that the parameters as evaluated by the ICT Experts, the Performance obtained the mean of 4.84 and interpreted as Highly Agree, the Graphics and Multimedia, and Lay-Outs both obtained the mean of 4.75 and both interpreted as Highly Agree. The Depth of Knowledge which obtained the mean of 4.66 and interpreted as Highly Agree. The Grand Mean is 4.72, all with an interpretation of Highly Agree.

The results connote that the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics was very highly accepted by the ICT Experts in terms of Graphics and Multimedia, Lay-outs, Operation, and Performance.

The findings of Mbayen (2013) confirms that the mobile application domain is in constant evolution. The evolution from the utilization of computers to the use of mobile application provides the idea that this trend is applied in education in which instructional materials are now being placed in these applications. With these, the evaluated learning material in terms of Graphics and Multimedia, Lay-outs, Operation, and Performance as assessed by the ICT experts shows that experts agree with the qualities placed in this mobile application as an effective learning material.

Enck, Oceau, Mcdaniel And Chaudhuri (2012) pointed that the rapid growth of smartphones has led to a renaissance for mobile services. This confirms the result that ICT experts believed that the development of instructional material through android application is an effective study.

The views expressed by the experts indicated that the developed mobile application was generally efficient, simple to learn, easy to navigate, appealing and engaging. It was also pedagogically constructive as the content and the tools used in the application were useful from the perspective of both the content experts and the IT experts. Thus, accomplishing the primary goal of this research study by providing effective instruction through mobile learning.

Having gone through the reflection process and analyzing the qualitative and quantitative data obtained using evaluative tool, the challenges in implementing the mobile learning application for the learners were identified using content analysis of the data.

Recommendations and Suggestions for the Improvement of the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials In Genetics by the Teachers of Science

Having gone through the process, it was felt that this research build on the principles of content experts and ICT experts which made the development of mobile learning application effective. This was due to the fact that the researcher and the developer were actively

involved throughout the whole process and supported each other to produce an effective mobile application.

Through the evaluation of the developed mobile application, content experts stated their suggestions for the improvement of the product.

According to Teacher A, “I think the possible limitation is that the learner is unable to zoom in or out the videos provided to really help learners to focus and understand the topic”, similar to the suggestion of Teacher B “The videos should be flexible enough so that learners can view it in different angles”

According to Teacher C, “The use of android applications may cause misconceptions about the certain topics particularly the difficult topics. Therefore, it must be clearly discussed, and if possible, maximize the use of application by providing students enrichment activities which can help them further understand the lesson”, this is similar to the observation of Teacher D “The teacher or instructor should explain how and when the application will be used and it should be coupled with instruction on how to do the activities”

Teacher E said that “The application is truly a valuable material in learning Genetics”.

The observations and recommendations of the Content experts are supported by the idea of Echevarria and Short (2012) which explains that, lesson preparation, building background, comprehensible input, strategies, interaction, practice and application, , and review and assessment are vital for proper lesson delivery.

Recommendations and Suggestions for the Improvement of the Developed Android-Based Learning Materials In Genetics by the IT Experts

The findings of the evaluation of the mobile application of ICT experts showed challenges with respect to development time, high production costs, technical and organizational issues, workload of academics and necessity of providing technical support both to remote students and faculty. Therefore, establishing adequate support structures for both teachers and students are essential for the sustenance of these innovative practices.

According to ICT Expert A, “There should be an automatic update of the content”, same as true with the suggestion of ICT Expert B “Although it operates offline, it should also be able to connect to the internet to update its version”.

According to ICT Expert C, “ As the title implies, it limits and only works for android users” similar to the suggestion of ICT Expert D, “The application should also be accessible for apple or ios users”

ICT Expert E recommends that “Since the videos can be watched offline, it will also takes space in the storage of the device. I suggest that for further development of the mobile application, maybe put an option where you can choose videos you currently want to be available offline so that only the needed ones taking up space and storage.” , similar to the suggestions of ICT Expert F that “storage and power consumptions needed to be considered”.

This finding is in line with Montreux et al.’s (2015) study where they also emphasized the importance of technical and pedagogical support to “stimulate teacher and student recognition of tablet devices’ potential in education.”

The design and development of any instructional material depend on the target audience, the subject content and the organizational culture of the institution (context). As such, the findings of this study may not have a universal value; however, these findings may throw light on some of the pedagogical, technological, social interaction and contextual attributes including cultural dimensions that have to be considered when designing mobile applications. It also provides guiding principles for designing both mobile solutions and on how to conduct developmental research in mobile learning.

Conclusions

In the light of the findings and in response to the problem posed in the research, the following conclusions were derived.

The developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics was generally efficient, simple to learn, easy to navigate, appealing and engaging. It was also pedagogically constructive as the content and the tools used in the application were useful from the perspective of both the content experts and the ICT experts. Thus, accomplishing the primary goal of this research study by providing effective instruction through mobile learning.

Based on the Conclusions, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

The developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics can be used to facilitate teaching-learning process.

The developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics maybe subjected to revision and modifications in the future depending on the needed competency for a particular topic and the needs and abilities and sustainability of learning styles of the future learners.

The developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics maybe subjected to be improvement to be utilized in IOS or apple devices.

The developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics may be modified for an automatic update of the content.

Encourage other teachers in science specifically Biology teachers to use the developed Android-Based Learning Materials in Genetics. Additional studies maybe conducted with regards to more content-based courses to be placed in other areas that could supplement the findings of this study.

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